

Table S1. Basic sample information for Australasian tektites from South China.

Sample ID	Type	Sampling Location	Morphology
GDMM	Splash-form	<i>Maoming, Guangdong Province</i>	oval
GDWC-1	Splash-form	<i>Wuchuan, Guangdong Province</i>	dumbbell
GDWC-S1	Splash-form	<i>Wuchuan, Guangdong Province</i>	sphere
GDWC-2	Splash-form	<i>Wuchuan, Guangdong Province</i>	disc
GDWC-D	Splash-form	<i>Wuchuan, Guangdong Province</i>	dumbbell
GDWC-T	Splash-form	<i>Wuchuan, Guangdong Province</i>	teardrop
GDZJ-S1	Splash-form	<i>Zhanjiang, Guangdong Province</i>	bark
GDZJ-S3	Splash-form	<i>Zhanjiang, Guangdong Province</i>	blocky
GDZJ-S4	Splash-form	<i>Zhanjiang, Guangdong Province</i>	oval
GDZJ-S5	Splash-form	<i>Zhanjiang, Guangdong Province</i>	large bark
GDZJ-S6	Splash-form	<i>Zhanjiang, Guangdong Province</i>	oval
GDZJ-S7	Splash-form	<i>Zhanjiang, Guangdong Province</i>	oval
GDZJ-S8	Splash-form	<i>Zhanjiang, Guangdong Province</i>	oval
GC	Splash-form	<i>Zhanjiang, Guangdong Province</i>	broken disc
ZW	Splash-form	<i>Zhanjiang, Guangdong Province</i>	broken oval
ZWC	Splash-form	<i>Zhanjiang, Guangdong Province</i>	sphere
DT	Splash-form	<i>Zhanjiang, Guangdong Province</i>	small blocky
GDLZ-2	Splash-form	<i>Leizhou, Guangdong Province</i>	broken oval
GDLZ-5	Splash-form	<i>Leizhou, Guangdong Province</i>	small bark
GDLZ-S1	Splash-form	<i>Leizhou, Guangdong Province</i>	small oval
GDLZ-S2	Splash-form	<i>Leizhou, Guangdong Province</i>	broken oval
GDLZ-S3	Splash-form	<i>Leizhou, Guangdong Province</i>	bark
GDLZ-S4	Splash-form	<i>Leizhou, Guangdong Province</i>	broken oval
WSD	Splash-form	<i>Leizhou, Guangdong Province</i>	broken blocky
EC	Splash-form	<i>Leizhou, Guangdong Province</i>	winding bark
GDXW	Splash-form	<i>Xuwen, Guangdong Province</i>	thin bark
GXYL-1	Splash-form	<i>Bobai, Guangxi Province</i>	small blocky
GXYL-S1	Splash-form	<i>Bobai, Guangxi Province</i>	sphere
GXYL-2	Splash-form	<i>Bobai, Guangxi Province</i>	teardrop
GXYL-S2	Splash-form	<i>Bobai, Guangxi Province</i>	sphere
GXYL-3	Splash-form	<i>Bobai, Guangxi Province</i>	teardrop

GXYL-S3	Splash-form	<i>Bobai, Guangxi Province</i>	teardrop
HNHK-S1	Splash-form	<i>Haikou, Hainan Province</i>	broken bark
HNHK-1	Splash-form	<i>Haikou, Hainan Province</i>	small broken bark
HNWC-1	Splash-form	<i>Wenchang, Hainan Province</i>	broken teardrop
BSP	Splash-form	<i>Wenchang, Hainan Province</i>	small blocky
GPZ	Splash-form	<i>Wenchang, Hainan Province</i>	bark
HNWN-1	Splash-form	<i>Wanning, Hainan Province</i>	small bark
HNDF-S1	Splash-form	<i>Dongfang, Hainan Province</i>	blocky, bark
HNCM	Splash-form	<i>Chengmai, Hainan Province</i>	small sphere
MNL	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	layered
MNK	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	blocky
HN-1	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	layered
HN-2	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	layered
HN-3	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	layered
HN-4	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	layered
HN-5	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	layered
HN-6	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	blocky
HN-7	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	layered
HN-8	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	layered
HN-9	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	layered
HN-10	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	layered
HN-11	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	layered
HN-12	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	layered
HN-13	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	layered
HN-14	Muong Nong-type	<i>Hainan Province</i>	layered